

Physical Maximization, $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ and Statistical Extremization Recipes

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 4, 2023

The idea of maximization of entropy as a physical maximization, say of disorder, seems to be entrenched in physics. Historically, it seems to follow from analyses of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. In particular, a traditional argument seems to be that if one has N particles (where N is very large) and a total amount of energy E , then there is no bias involved in the distribution of E among these N particles. Each “arrangement” carries the same weight. As a result, one wants to include all arrangements which is equivalent to saying that one wants to physically maximize the number of arrangements subject to the constraint $E = \text{total energy}$. Thus there is a physical reason for maximization. This physical maximization is equivalent to the property that $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ i.e. one only considers energy distribution and does not need to resolve the particles so to speak. {This property is equivalent to: $p(e_1)p(e_2)\dots p(e_N) = p(E)$ so all distributions of E carry the same weight or probability.} The equation $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$, however, automatically yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution without the need of any maximization calculus. The traditional alternative is to calculate the number of arrangements $N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$, take \ln and extremize it with respect to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i)$. N is assumed to be large and Stirling’s approximation is used. Both of these approaches are identical because there is a physical maximization in the problem which leads to the same result: $P(e_i)P(e_j)=P(e_i+e_j)$.

Although no maximization is needed to solve the above problem, maximization seems to have been adopted as a fundamental physical principle even in problems for which $P(e_i)P(e_j)$ is not equal to $P(e_i+e_j)$. An example is a power law distribution, i.e. $p(e_i/T) = (e_i/T)^g / Z$ where g is a constant and Z a normalization factor.

The arrangement problem ($p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$) finds a specific form for the function to be maximized, namely $n(e_i) \ln\{n(e_i)\}$. This in turn leads to a specific distribution i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann. If one starts with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, however, one may work backwards and find a function of probability which when maximized subject to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)$ yields $p(e_i)$. This function need not have anything to do with physical arrangements. As a result, this procedure lends itself to a recipe which holds for any probability distribution, even for ones in which $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ is not equal to $p(e_i+e_j)$. In such a case, it is not at all clear what one tries to maximize physically, but the recipe still holds.

The recipe involves taking $p(e_i/T)$ and solving for e_i/T i.e. $e_i/T = \text{Function}(p(e_i/T))$. One then integrates this function with respect to $dp(e_i/T)$ so that the derivative $d/dp(e_i)$, which is the inverse operation, returns e_i/T . This matches $1/T d/dp(e_i) \text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)$ from the constraint immediately leading to an extremization procedure. The point is that there seems to be no physical maximization involved whatsoever. It is true, however, that one finds a function $p(e_i)$, with no e_i explicitly present, such that small changes to $p(e_i)$ with $\text{Sum over } i d(p(e_i)) = 0$ and $\text{Sum over } i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$ leads to 0. Physically, these constraints hold in a system and one may imagine fluctuations leading to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$. The function of $p(e_i)$ might be considered a stability function and thus be associated with equilibrium, but we argue that this does not necessarily have anything to do with any physical maximization. Thus this kind of recipe-based entropy may be better thought of as a stability function than a measure of the maximization of arrangements (sometimes called the maximization of disorder).

Distributed Quantity Which Probabilistically Is Not Distinguished By Its Holders

A Maxwell-Boltzmann gas consists of particles (e.g. molecules) which are described by the piece of information, energy, which is conserved. Thus there are N particles and a total of E (energy). Each particle has its own energy value and collisions occur so that any given particle may change its energy value in time. The idea seems to be that if the system is equilibrium, the number of particles with e_i (a given number) does not change in time. We argue, however, that the idea is more general. One really seeks the probability for an energy value regardless of how it is distributed over a number of particles. In other words, the following relationship holds:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j) \quad ((1))$$

Thus one may distribute energy among the particles every possible way, with each distribution being equally likely. Simply looking at ((1)), if one had $e_i+e_j=E$, then all e_i+e_j possibilities are equally likely. This idea carries over to all particles as ((1)) may be generalized to

$$p(e_i)p(e_j)p(e_k) = p(e_i+e_j+e_k) \text{ etc } ((2))$$

{As an aside, this same type of distribution appears in free particle quantum mechanics where $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$.}

Thus one wishes to consider all distributions of the total energy E over N particles, with each distribution or arrangement carrying the same weight. In other words, one wishes to maximize the amount of arrangements. This is a physical requirement. As a result, one may carry out a specific calculation of the number of arrangements, namely:

$$\# \text{ arrangements} = N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \quad \text{where } n(e_i) = Np(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

Next, one may take \ln of ((3)) and use Stirling's approximation $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N)$ for large N . The last step is to maximize this quantity with respect to $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i p(e_i)$. The result leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, i.e. one maximizes:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) - 1/T \sum e_i p(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

The point we wish to make is that a physical maximization actually occurs, although the problem may be solved, as noted, using $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ (taking \ln of both sides) and not using maximization at all. ((4)), which is cast in the form of an extremization, is associated with a physical maximization, gives rise to a "recipe" because $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. We argue that it is really the form \ln (logarithm) which is linked with physical maximization (i.e. arrangements as $\ln(n(e_i))$

also appears there using Stirling's approximation) i.e. $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ and not the overall recipe approach of ((4)). We discuss this further in the next section.

Extremization Recipe

As noted above, extremization may be established as a recipe which has nothing to do with physical maximization. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, the idea of maximization of arrangements, which is a physical idea, does not have to be cast in the form of variational calculus, it follows directly from $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$.

Given any probability distribution, even one for which $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ does not equal $p(e_i+e_j)$ and hence there is no physical maximization of arrangements (maximization of disorder etc), the maximization of entropy recipe still holds. An example is a power law distribution:

$$p(e_i/T) = (e_i/T)^g / Z \text{ where } g \text{ is a constant and } Z \text{ is the normalization } ((5))$$

The recipe involves taking any probability distribution which is a function of e_i/T and writing e_i/T as a function of the probability i.e. $\text{Function}(p(e_i/T))$ such that no e_i appears explicitly. This function is then integrated over $dp(e_i)$ and called "entropy". Taking the derivative with respect to $d/dp(e_i)$ is the inverse relationship to integration so one obtains e_i/T , but this matches e_i/T from a constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. Thus an extremization recipe always exists even if no physical maximization occurs. As a result, it is not clear why one should think of entropy in terms of physical maximization if $p(e_i)p(e_j) \neq p(e_i+e_j)$ as in the power law case.

Mathematically, however, one may create the "entropy" function such that its derivative with respect to $p(e_i)$ returns e_i/T . This seems to be done frequently in the literature. In such a case, the "entropy" function seems to be more of a stability function. In a physical system, $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E$ are constant, yet fluctuations may change an equilibrium probability distribution. If a fluctuation changes $p(e_i)$ such that there is a kind of domino effect, one would consider the equilibrium to be unstable at best. Thus one might expect there to exist a function which when perturbed slightly in terms of $p(e_i)$ yields 0 (with constraints considered) i.e. is an extremized function. One might argue that this describes a stable equilibrium even if no physical maximization occurs.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of entropy linked to microscopic maximization of arrangements (or disorder) really follows from $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$. This relation allows one to solve for $p(e_i)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann type distribution without any mathematical extremization process. $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$, however, is equivalent to a physical maximization of arrangements because any $e_i+e_j=E$ have equal weight. This may be extended to $p(e_1)p(e_2)...p(e_n)=E$. Thus one may also write an expression for the total number of physical arrangements of total energy E distributed among N particles. For N very large, one may take \ln and use Stirling's approximation. Finally, the expression (which represents a physical number of arrangements, not just an arbitrary function of $p(e_i)$) may be extremized subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. This also yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

The latter approach gives rise to an extremization recipe which may be used even in the case in which $p(e_i)p(e_j) \neq p(e_i+e_j)$ i.e. in the case in which no physical maximization occurs. An example is a power law probability $p(e_i/T) = (e_i/T)^{-\alpha}/Z$. The recipe for a given probability distribution is to use $p(e_i/T)$ to solve for e_i/T in terms of a Function($p(e_i/T)$) with no e_i explicitly present. One may then integrate with respect to $dp(e_i)$ to create an "entropy" function. Taking the derivative with respect to $p(e_i)$, which is the inverse operation, returns e_i/T which matches e_i/T from the constraint $1/T \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. No physical maximization seems to occur at all. This recipe based entropy, however, does describe a function which is "stable" with respect to small changes in $p(e_i)$ with $\sum_i dp(e_i)=0$ and $\sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$. In other words, it describes a kind of "stability" function for equilibrium even if $p(e_i)p(e_j) \neq p(e_i+e_j)$ and no physical maximization is present (in terms of arrangements).